

Expanding PVLIB Python for Modeling Static CPV Systems

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INTRODUCTION TO INTEGRATED-MICROTRACKING CPV SYSTEMS

Concentrator Photovoltaics (CPV) has shown very high conversion efficiencies (> 40%) but suffers from a major limitation: it has to employ very precise external two-axis tracking structures to align the modules to the direct irradiance, which highly increase installation costs and prevents their use on rooftop applications. The Swiss company Insolight has developed a CPV system with integrated planar microtracking enabling its installation on a fixed structure without the need an external moving tracker, which is compatible with rooftop applications. The module uses III-V multi-junction solar cells under concentration and a size close to 1 mm, which reduces the form factor to a few centimeters. A 29% module efficiency at Concentrator Standard Test Conditions (IEC 62670-1) has been demonstrated outdoors, which can lead to a large gain in energy yield. Some challenges remain, like the optimization of the optical system to collect very wide angles of incidence.

FIGURE 1. Insolight test module installed at a fixed tilt at UPM (right) and schematic of operation of the micro-planar tracking system. Direct beam irradiance is focused on a 1mm III-V cell. For AOI not equal to 0°, the biconvex lens translates the focus and a simple mechanism causes the backplane to follow the focal point.

CPV SYSTEM MODELING

The Sandia Array Performance Model has been extended in the past to describe the distinct behavior of CPV systems with external two-axis tracking [1]. However, this adaptation requires fitting a large set of empirical coefficients which are not directly related to physical quantities so we find it difficult to implement. The very popular PVSyst tool also includes a method for considering two-axis tracked CPV, through the definition of some derating factors (Utilization Factors UF) that describe the additional losses produced by some parameters like the CPV lens sensitivity to module temperature or the non-linear current mismatch between the subcells of the multi-junction cells produced by the variations on the solar spectrum. The spectrum is approximated by air mass and lens temperature by the ambient temperature [2], [3]. Optical efficiency dependence on the clearness of the sky can also be considered through DNI. Each UF is a piecewise linear approximation of the nonlinear behavior of module efficiency versus those quantities. As shown in Equations 1 and 2, the global UF is a weighted sum of the UF for each parameter of interest.

$$UF = \sum_{i=1}^n w_i \cdot UF_i \quad (1)$$

$$UF_i = \begin{cases} 1 + (x - x_{thld}) \cdot S_{x \leq x_{thld}} & \text{if } x \leq x_{thld} \\ 1 + (x - x_{thld}) \cdot S_{x > x_{thld}} & \text{if } x > x_{thld} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where UF is the global Utilization Factor, UF_i is the utilization factor for each parameter, w_i is the weight for that parameter x , x_{thld} is the value of the quantity at the threshold and S is the slope of each UF . Slopes, thresholds and weights of a specific module are determined empirically [3]. We chose this model to be implemented in PVLIB for its simplicity. In our work, we extended the modeling to consider the distinct sensitivity of the optical efficiency of Insolight static CPV module versus the angle of incidence (AOI). A new UF_{AOI} is introduced to take AOI into account in static panels in general, which is used as in Equation 3:

$$UF = UF_{\text{AOI}} \cdot \sum_{i=2}^n w_i \cdot UF_i \quad (3)$$

PVLIB MODEL FOR CPV

In order to implement the model in PVLIB, the module `cpvsystem.py` has been created. In this module, a new class called `CPVSystem` has been developed, which allows to model a typical CPV system mounted on a dual axis tracker. For its implementation, the example of the `PVSystem` class has been followed, using the functions of this class where possible. The necessary methods to calculate the `PVSystem` utilization factors for each parameter have been added and a function to calculate the overall `UF` has been added. In addition, the `LocalizedCPVSystem` class has been added, which adds the functions of the `Location` class to the `CPVSystem` class. Finally, the functions needed to automatically study the module parameters necessary to calculate the `UF` have been incorporated.

PVLIB MODEL FOR INTEGRATED-TRACKING CPV

It has been developed a new class called `StaticCPVSystem` that allows to model a CPV system that has integrated tracking and is mounted on a static support. This class includes functions to calculate the AOI and its corresponding `UF`. Likewise, it has been added the `LocalizedStaticCPVSystem` class.

FIGURE 2. Functional block diagram of the model developed

FIGURE 3. Simplified UML diagram for the static CPV model

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